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Returns and Return Policies

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List of abbreviations

ABRS	Area-Based Return Support
ACHR	Access Centre for Human Rights
CAT	Convention Against Torture
CSOs	Civil Society Organizations
EU	European Union
Euromed Rights	Euro-Mediterranean Human Rights Network
GSO	General Security Office
HDC	Higher Defence Council
HRW	Human Rights Watch
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
ISF	Internal Security Forces
OCHA	United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
SARC	Syrian Arab Red Crescent
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UNSC	United Nations Security Council
US	United States

Summary

This country dossier examines the governance of return migration from Libya to Nigeria, conducted as part of WP4 of the *GAPS–Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond* project. Based on a range of primary and secondary data, it explores the regional and international dynamics influencing return migration. Libya, a North African country with a significant Mediterranean coastline, was once an immigration hub under the leadership of Muammar Gaddafi, who ruled from 1969 until his fall in 2011. Gaddafi’s Pan-African policies attracted labour from across Africa, including Nigeria, a populous West African nation. However, following Gaddafi’s ousting, Libya transitioned into a primary transit point for sub-Saharan African migrants aiming to reach Europe. The ensuing political vacuum allowed militias to gain control over crucial migration routes and detention facilities, making migration governance even more challenging. Return migration from Libya can be voluntary or forced. The Voluntary Humanitarian Return (VHR) program, managed by the International Organization for Migration (IOM) with financial support from the European Union (EU), aids migrants who choose to go back home. However, the “voluntary” aspect is complicated, as many migrants opt for this path due to the harsh and often abusive conditions in detention centres. Forced returns, where migrants are detained and deported under coercion, are associated with significant human rights abuses. The actors in return migration governance include the Libyan Government of National Unity (GNU), which has limited control, militias that profit from migration through detention and smuggling operations, and international organizations like the IOM. The Libyan Coast Guard, funded in part by the EU, intercepts migrants attempting to cross the Mediterranean and returns them to shore, often resulting in detention. The EU plays a significant role in influencing these practices through funding agreements such as the 2017 Italy-Libya Memorandum of Understanding, aimed at curbing migration flows to Europe. However, these agreements have faced criticism for prioritizing border control over the welfare of migrants. Libya’s internal drivers of migration governance focus on national security and economic strain, prompting strict controls and reliance on non-state actors like militias. Externally, the EU’s desire to reduce irregular migration has led to substantial financial investments in programs to support return and reintegration. Nevertheless, these programs are often viewed as mechanisms to shift the responsibility of migration management to transit countries like Libya. Limited infrastructure, corruption, and fragmented authority exacerbate the challenges of effective and humane governance. The consequences of these practices are profound. Migrants in Libya often face inadequate protection, with many held in detention centres known for poor conditions and abuse. Policies that restrict movement result in enforced immobility, trapping migrants in a country unable to provide safe passage or return options. Diplomatic relations between Libya, the EU, and sub-Saharan African countries, such as Nigeria, are strained, as origin countries struggle to reintegrate returnees with minimal support. This dossier emphasizes the need for policies that integrate border control with comprehensive humanitarian considerations to address the root causes of migration while protecting migrants’ rights.

Keywords: Return Migration, Governance, Africa, European Union, Libya, Nigeria

GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by de-centring the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examine the shortcomings of EU’s return governance;
- analyse enablers and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explore the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- a focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance fissures;
- an analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU Member States and with third countries hinder cooperation on return; and
- a trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is an interdisciplinary 3-year project (2023-2026), co-coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on 4 continents. GAPs' fieldwork has been conducted in 14 countries: Jordan, Lebanon, Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

This country dossier has been compiled in the context of the GAPs Work Package on ‘Return Migration Governance in the African and Middle Eastern Regions and the Role of the EU.’

Since the vast majority of migrants and refugees move and reside in and among countries in the immediate region of their origin countries, return migration will also predominantly take place within the region of countries in crisis. Yet, scholarly concerns have overwhelmingly focused on the minority of migrants who travelled further afield, in particular to the European Union, and return from there to their regions of origin. Relatively little attention has been given to return policies of neighbouring receiving states in the Global South.

Disregarding this regional dimension puts a Eurocentric bias on the study of return migration governance. Regional return governance, moreover, both shapes and is shaped by the externalization and return migration policies of the EU. On the one hand, the EU’s deterrence and externalization ‘partnerships’ fundamentally affect return diplomacies, infrastructures, and trajectories in its neighbouring regions. On the other hand, the governance of regional returns has repercussions the migration dynamics the EU seeks to control, for its engagement with ‘third countries,’ and for the international norms it claims to uphold.

To address this knowledge gap, therefore, this Work Package has the aim to better understand the intersections between (i) return migration governance within the African and Middle Eastern regions and (ii) the role of the European Union and its external migration policy. To this end, it asks three core research questions: (i) What characterizes return migration governance within African and Middle Eastern regions? Specifically: how are these modalities shaped by the EU’s external migration policy?; (ii) What are the driving forces behind these types of return migration governance? Specifically: how are these drivers affected by the EU’s

external migration policy?; and (iii) What are the effects of these drivers and modalities of regional migration governance, for both people and policy? Specifically: what are the implications of specific regional return migration governance for the EU's external migration policy? The Work Package answers these questions for eight 'host countries' (Iraq, Jordan, Lebanon, Türkiye, Iran, Morocco, Tunisia, Libya) focused on three 'origin countries' (Syria, Afghanistan, Nigeria).

Research in this Work Package is carried out in an embedded-multiple case study design, in which cases are selected for diversity (encompassing variation in return types) and representativeness (including main host countries in return systems that are salient to Europe, i.e., Africa, the broader Middle East). Data are generated through document analysis (a minimum of 20 documents – including academic papers, expert report, and media coverage – has been analyzed in-depth per country dossier) and 10 (semi-structured, in-depth) expert interviews (with state authorities, international organizations, and civil society actors) have been conducted. Data was coded iteratively. First deductively, through a common codebook based on a shared conceptual framework developed to answer the three core questions listed above. Particular attention here is paid to modalities (legal, policy and operational infrastructures), drivers (capacity and interests of actors), and outcomes (monitoring mechanisms and expert views on sustainability of returns). Second, data was coded inductively, highlighting emerging themes that were not included in the codebook but that nevertheless surfaced as contextually relevant. Research has been subject to ethical review of the host institutions of the individual researchers conducting the country-specific research. The core concern here has been to ensure (oral) informed consent for interviews on the basis of full anonymity of interlocutors. Document and interview analysis have been synthesized through two workshops dedicated to these specific research phases.

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Introduction

This country dossier has been compiled in the context of the Horizon Europe project “GAPS– ‘Decentering the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond” and, more specifically, Work Package 4, which relates to ‘Return Migration Governance in the African and Middle Eastern Regions and the Role of the EU.’

Since most migrants and refugees move and reside in and among countries in the immediate region of their origin countries, return migration will also predominantly take place within the region of countries in crisis. Yet, scholarly concerns have overwhelmingly focused on the minority of migrants who travelled further afield, in particular to the European Union, and return from there to their regions of origin. Relatively little attention has been given to return policies of neighbouring receiving states in the Global South. Studying this regional dimension can remedy the Eurocentric bias on the study of return migration governance. At the same time, the European dimension needs to be taken into account when looking at return governance within the African and Middle Eastern region, for it both shapes and is shaped by the externalization and return migration policies of the EU. On the one hand, the EU’s deterrence and externalization ‘partnerships’ as well as various migration diplomacy ‘deals’ fundamentally affect return infrastructures and trajectories in its neighbouring regions. On the other hand, the governance of regional returns has repercussions the migration dynamics the EU seeks to control, for its engagement with ‘third countries,’ and for the international norms it claims to uphold.

To address this knowledge gap, therefore, this Work Package aims to better understand the intersections between (i) return migration governance within the African and Middle Eastern regions and (ii) the role of the European Union and its external migration policy. To this end, it asks three core research questions: (i) What characterizes return migration governance within African and Middle Eastern regions? Specifically: how are these modalities shaped by the EU’s external migration policy?; (ii) What are the driving forces behind these types of return migration governance? Specifically: how are these drivers affected by the EU’s external migration policy?; and (iii) What are the effects of these drivers and modalities of regional migration governance, for both people and policy? Specifically: what are the implications of specific regional return migration governance for the EU’s external migration policy? The Work Package answers these questions for eight ‘host countries’ (Iraq, Jordan, Lebanon, Türkiye, Iran, Morocco, Tunisia, Libya) focused on three ‘origin countries’ (Syria, Afghanistan, Nigeria).

A significant example of return migration governance is the repatriation of Nigerian migrants from Libya. Following the political and social upheavals post-2011, Libya became a prominent transit hub for sub-Saharan Africans, including many Nigerians. Di Maio’s analysis emphasizes that Libya serves as the largest migration hub in North Africa, drawing migrants from over 44 nationalities, with migration routes influenced heavily by regional conflict and economic opportunities (Di Maio, Leone Sciabolazza, and Molini 2023). This group often endures severe hardships, such as violence, detention, and human rights abuses at the hands of both state and non-state actors in Libya. In response, the IOM’s Voluntary Humanitarian Return (VHR) program, funded in part by the EU, has been pivotal in facilitating the return of these individuals. The case of Nigeria illustrates the intersection of EU external migration policies and regional return strategies, highlighting the challenges of balancing security, humanitarian aid, and ethical governance in migration management. This dossier explores

how these complex dynamics shape return migration practices in Libya, offering insights into the broader implications for both regional and EU-level policies.

Methods

Research in this Work Package is carried out in an embedded-multiple case study design, in which cases are selected for diversity (encompassing variation in return types) and representativeness (including main host countries in return systems that are salient to Europe, i.e., Africa, the broader Middle East). Data are generated through document analysis – including academic papers, expert report, and media coverage – and interviews (semi-structured, in-depth key expert interviews (with state authorities, international organizations, and civil society actors). Data is coded iteratively, in two rounds: First deductively, through a common codebook based on a shared conceptual framework developed to answer the three core questions listed above. Particular attention here is paid to modalities (legal, policy and operational infrastructures), drivers (capacity and interests of actors), and outcomes (monitoring mechanisms and expert views on sustainability of returns). Second inductively, highlighting emerging themes not included in the codebook that are nevertheless deemed contextually relevant. Research has been subject to ethical review of the host institutions of the individual researchers conducting the country-specific research. The core concern here has been to ensure (oral) informed consent for interviews on the basis of full anonymity and untraceability of interlocutors. Document and interview analysis has been synthesized throughout Work Package by means of two workshops dedicated to these specific research phases.

Data collection for the Libya-Nigeria case involved an extensive review of written primary and secondary sources, including academic articles, policy reports from the EU and the International Organization for Migration (IOM), NGO briefings, and media coverage. This document analysis provided foundational insights into return migration governance and informed the context for further inquiry. Given Libya's politically unstable environment since the 2011 uprisings, on-site data collection was not feasible. The security risks and fragmented state control limited travel, making direct fieldwork impossible. Still, to triangulate the findings from these documents, four targeted interviews were conducted with key informants. The main respondent (R1) was a former Libyan diplomat and international affairs consultant for the Libyan transitional government from 2015 to 2020. Another participant (R2) was an NGO activist who previously worked with the Libyan Commission of Civil Society in Tripoli. The final two respondents were researchers—one British and one Libyan (R3, R4)—who contributed responses to specific questions during the discussion. These respondents requested anonymity. These interviews were held online to ensure safety and accessibility amid restricted travel conditions. The politically charged nature of migration within Libyan politics presented further challenges, making additional interviews impractical, as many stakeholders were reluctant to engage or share information openly.

Access to participants was facilitated through established connections with academics, NGOs, and international organizations involved in migration efforts, building trust and ensuring informed consent with guarantees of anonymity, while ensuring that no questions asked would violate this principle. This cautious approach was crucial for gathering candid insights in a context where discussing migration governance remains sensitive. Despite these challenges, combining interview data with document analysis enabled a comprehensive understanding of

return migration governance and highlighted the socio-political complexities impacting the return from Nigerian migrants in Libya.

Context

Libya is a country belonging to all Africans [...] What we call clandestine migration is a totally natural phenomenon [...] It is normal that Africans move around their own land [...] Free yourself from the efforts that you are making now to control borders: surveillance along frontiers, custom control, immigration and security [...] Leave people free to move and to look for a job from one place to another.

Colonel Muammar Gaddafi, 2005 (cited in Paoletti and Pastore 2010, 10)

Libya holds a significant position in both South-South and South-North migration dynamics, transitioning over time from being an attractive immigration destination to a strategic transit country for migrants heading to Europe. This shift is embedded in Libya's complex socio-political and economic developments, particularly since the discovery of oil in 1959, which spurred labour migration from across Africa. Under Colonel Muammar Gaddafi's rule from 1969 to 2011, Libya's Pan-African policies promoted the inflow of labour migrants, including those from sub-Saharan Africa, to support its expanding economy. This period established strong migration networks and positioned Libya as a primary destination for work (for the country's political background, please see Vandewalle 2012; on migration, specifically: Tsourapas 2017).

Outmigration from Nigeria has been driven by a mix of socio-economic, political, and environmental factors. Economic instability, marked by high unemployment and persistent poverty, has historically pushed Nigerians to seek better opportunities abroad. The country's dependence on oil revenues contributes to economic volatility, limiting stable job markets and exacerbating inequalities (Arhin-Sam 2019). Additionally, political unrest, particularly in the north due to insurgent activities by groups like Boko Haram, has further fuelled migration as individuals flee violence and insecurity. Social aspirations, such as improved education and living standards, also play an essential role in migration decisions, reinforcing movement patterns towards countries like Libya. Environmental challenges, including droughts and floods, have impacted agricultural livelihoods, pushing many rural Nigerians to look beyond their borders for stability (on the broader regional context, see: Adesina 2021).

Libya's transition from an immigration hub to a transit point for migrants was influenced by a range of factors. During Gaddafi's era, the country maintained open policies towards African labour, bolstered by agreements that encouraged cross-border movement (Paoletti 2011). Gaddafi's migration policies were not just economic measures but part of a broader strategy of migration diplomacy, utilizing cross-border mobility as a tool for cooperative and coercive diplomatic engagements with neighbouring states (Tsourapas 2017). However, the early 2000s marked the start of stricter immigration controls, motivated by collaboration with European partners aiming to reduce irregular migration (Joffé 2011). The 2011 civil war, which ended Gaddafi's rule, marked a turning point as it dismantled centralized governance and left a fragmented state where various militias and non-state actors exploited migration routes for profit. The combination of weakened border controls and the proliferation of smuggling networks entrenched Libya's role as a key transit country.

This shift from being a destination to a transit state was fuelled by policies that increasingly irregularised migration. Legislative changes at home and abroad, including the adoption of international anti-smuggling protocols and varied attempts at reforming labour legislation, contributed to a situation where many migrants found themselves “irregular” under shifting legal frameworks (World Bank 2015). Collaborations with the EU to manage migration flows led to a paradox where Libya needed migrant labour but became a gateway for those looking to reach Europe (Ceccorulli 2022). The absence of a unified authority following the 2011 uprisings further compounded these dynamics, allowing militias and armed groups to control parts of the migration process and establish smuggling routes.

For Nigerian migrants arriving in Libya, the reality often contrasts starkly with their expectations. Initially drawn by prospects of employment in Libya’s oil, construction, and service sectors, many now find themselves trapped in a cycle of exploitation and violence. The socio-economic environment has become more hostile, with frequent reports of forced labour, extortion, and detention. These conditions are exacerbated by Libya’s fragmented power structure, where militias and informal authorities operate with impunity. Social discrimination further compounds these challenges, as sub-Saharan African migrants, including Nigerians, face systemic racism that reinforces their vulnerability. This discrimination limits access to legal employment and exposes them to abuse, perpetuating a state of economic and social limbo (Amnesty International 2020).

Migration numbers from Nigeria to Libya have reflected broader regional trends shaped by socio-economic challenges. Under Gaddafi, Libya attracted significant numbers of Nigerian workers, but this flow transformed in the post-2011 period as Libya became a transit country. As of 2024, the International Organization for Migration (IOM) reports that around 30,964 Nigerian migrants reside in Libya, representing about 4% of the total migrant population. The use of routes through Niger and Chad remains significant, funnelling migrants to entry points like Tomu and Matan al-Sarra in southern Libya. However, these routes have become increasingly perilous, marked by extreme desert conditions and control by armed groups.

The experience of Nigerian migrants is deeply intertwined with Libya’s political landscape. The power struggle between the Government of National Unity (GNU) in Tripoli, the Libyan National Army (LNA) led by Khalifa Haftar, and various militias creates a volatile environment where control is often fragmented. This instability allows non-state actors to exert significant influence over migration, turning it into a profitable enterprise through detention and human smuggling (Bish 2024). Migrants frequently become pawns in these power plays, facing arbitrary detention, violence, and extortion. The involvement of militias in detention operations and human trafficking adds another layer of complexity, making formal efforts to manage migration and ensure human rights more difficult.

These political and socio-economic developments have direct repercussions for Libya’s current return migration governance. The EU and IOM’s Voluntary Humanitarian Return (VHR) program has played a crucial role in facilitating the return of migrants, including Nigerians, to their home countries. However, the fractured nature of Libya’s governance has hindered these efforts, fostering corruption and complicating coordination among stakeholders. Migrants often have to pay bribes to expedite their return, reflecting the challenges of operating within an environment dominated by informal power structures.

The significance of migration routes into Libya is highlighted by Map 1, below, which depicts key entry points from West Africa. These routes illustrate how migration pathways converge

in Libya, underscoring the strategic nature of its southern borders. The map also demonstrates the importance of Niger and Chad as the two primary transit states for migrants reaching Libya, highlighting their roles as critical gateways for the journey. Additionally, it underscores the diversity of transit migrants, including individuals from countries as varied as Cameroon—who often transit through Nigeria to reach Libya—Guinea, and Somalia. This visual context not only provides geographical insight but symbolizes the complex migrants face as they navigate territories controlled by various states. Understanding these routes is essential to grasp the multi-layered challenges in addressing return migration governance within Libya.

Map 1 Major migration routes into Libya, 2024 (IOM 2024)

Findings

‘If I walk to the [police] station, they tell me to show my passport. If I do not have a passport, they tell me I am an illegal migrant and will be taken to a detention centre [...] If you go to complain against someone in the police, maybe his cousin or brother is in an armed group and that is why you are afraid for your life and cannot go to the law.’

Tripoli-based refugee (quoted in Amnesty International 2020)

Characteristics of Return Migration Governance from Libya to Nigeria

Return migration governance from Libya to Nigeria operates within a framework shaped by multiple challenges, including political fragmentation, the role of non-state actors, and international influence. Understanding the scale, types, key actors, policies, and practices involved is essential for comprehending the scope and impact of migration management in this corridor. The scale of return migration from Libya is significant but varies over time, influenced by Libya’s internal conflicts and international migration policies. Spatial network analysis by Di Maio further illustrates how conflict zones shape these flows, impacting both internal and external migration routes (Di Maio, Leone Sciabolazza, and Molini 2023). The International Organization for Migration (IOM) has facilitated the return of more than 80,000 migrants, including a substantial number of Nigerians, through the Voluntary Humanitarian Return (VHR) program since 2015. These figures, however, do not capture the entire picture, as the number of migrants in Libya is difficult to determine due to underreporting and the clandestine nature of migration. One interviewee, a former Libyan diplomat, emphasized that “many migrants prefer to stay hidden, knowing the risks of being identified and detained” (R1). This hidden aspect of migration underscores the scale of movement that remains undocumented, complicating efforts to manage and monitor returns effectively.

The types of return migration may be broadly categorized into voluntary and forced returns. The VHR program is the primary mechanism for voluntary returns, providing a way for migrants to return home with logistical and financial support from the IOM and the European Union (EU). Nigeria has the highest number of individuals participating in the Voluntary Humanitarian Return from Libya, with 4,127 returns, indicating significant engagement in the program compared to other countries (Graph 1). However, the “voluntary” aspect of these returns is contentious. Interview data indicates that many migrants choose to return only after enduring extreme conditions in detention or failing to secure a passage to Europe. “Voluntary return becomes the only option when migrants face indefinite detention and abuse,” noted R4. This highlights how voluntary returns are often driven by dire circumstances rather than genuine choice.

Forced returns are more coercive, involving detention and deportation by Libyan authorities or militias. These deportations are often accompanied by significant human rights abuses, as reported in multiple documents and confirmed by interviews (Amnesty International 2020). Detention centres, many controlled by militias rather than the state, have become profitable sites of severe violations, including torture, forced labour, and extortion. “Detention centres

are essentially profit hubs for militias, exploiting migrants for financial gain,” explained R3. This practice blurs the line between voluntary and forced returns, as even those who choose to leave do so under considerable duress. The situational approach of Bish et al (2024) highlights cases where migrants negotiate sea crossings to escape detention, thus transitioning from trafficking into smuggling.

Graph 1 – Voluntary Humanitarian Return from Libya by Country of Return (2018)

Key actors in the governance of return migration from Libya include state and non-state players, international organizations, and external powers such as the EU. The Libyan Government of National Unity (GNU) nominally oversees migration policy, but its control is limited due to political fragmentation. These policies are underpinned by strategic non-regulation, where selective inaction and ambiguous enforcement create an environment of controlled unpredictability (on this feature of migration governance, see Natter, Norman, and Stel 2023). This strategy is evident in how detention centres are operated and how return processes are managed, leveraging non-regulation for maintaining control. Real power frequently lies with militias and armed groups that control detention centres and profit from human smuggling and detention operations. “Militias have positioned themselves as both

protectors and perpetrators in the migration landscape,” commented R2. These groups often facilitate migration as part of a broader strategy for economic survival, highlighting the dual role of smuggling as both a criminal act and a response to socio-economic pressures, as noted by Sanchez (Sanchez 2020). The role of militias in migration management reflects the fragmented nature of governance, which echoes the coercive migration strategies identified in Gaddafi’s era, where migration was used as leverage to secure political and material benefits from European counterparts (Tsourapas 2017). The Libyan Coast Guard also plays a significant role, intercepting boats and returning migrants to shore, often leading to detention in facilities controlled by non-state actors.

International organizations like the IOM are critical for facilitating returns and supporting reintegration, yet they operate within a constrained environment shaped by Libya’s unstable political landscape. The EU, a significant external actor, exerts considerable influence through funding and policy frameworks aimed at reducing the flow of migrants to Europe. However, these measures often prioritize containment over the well-being of migrants. R1 pointed out that “European policies focus more on stopping migrants at any cost, sometimes disregarding the humanitarian aspect,” underlining the criticisms of such external interventions.

Policies governing return migration are influenced by both national legislation and international agreements. One of the most prominent is the 2017 Memorandum of Understanding between Libya and Italy, which sought to stem the tide of irregular migration through financial and logistical support to the Libyan Coast Guard and the construction of detention centres (Ceccorulli 2022). While these policies have been effective in reducing the number of migrants reaching Europe, they have also faced severe criticism for facilitating human rights abuses. “Policies that funnel money into Libya’s migration infrastructure without oversight end up empowering the wrong actors,” R3 noted.

Practices related to return migration are inconsistent due to Libya’s fractured political environment. While the IOM’s programs aim for humane repatriation, the reality on the ground varies dramatically. Some detention centres cooperate with NGOs to facilitate humane treatment, while others are run by militias that prioritize profit over the welfare of detainees. “You have centres that cooperate with international bodies and others that run like private fiefdoms,” R4 described. Corruption further complicates these practices, as reports indicate that migrants sometimes need to pay bribes to be released or prioritized for return. The fragmented governance structure means that while some policies align with international human rights standards, their implementation is patchy and subject to local power dynamics.

The practice of return migration is influenced by external funding, primarily from the EU. The EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa has channelled millions of euros into programs designed to curb irregular migration through returns and reintegration efforts. However, these programs are often criticized for their focus on containment rather than sustainable solutions that address the root causes of migration. “Financial support from the EU is vital, but when it prioritizes stopping migration over improving migrant conditions, it becomes problematic,” R1 observed. The governance practices have led to mixed outcomes for migrants and the institutions involved. On the one hand, voluntary return programs provide a pathway for some to return home safely. On the other hand, the presence of powerful non-state actors and inconsistent enforcement of policies contribute to ongoing abuse and exploitation. The dual reality of policy on paper versus practice on the ground reflects the deep-rooted challenges in migration governance from Libya to Nigeria. As R4 concluded, “policies are written with good

intentions, but without robust oversight, they can be hijacked by those with their own agendas.”

Drivers of Return Migration Governance from Libya to Nigeria

The governance of return migration from Libya to Nigeria is driven by a combination of domestic, external, and geopolitical forces. These forces shape the motivations, capacities, and roles that various actors play in return migration governance. The analysis below explores the interests, capacities, and the specific role of the European Union (EU) as a key driver in this framework.

The interests driving return migration governance are multifaceted and vary between domestic and external actors. Domestically, Libya’s government and local power structures arguably prioritize return migration governance as part of their broader national security and socio-economic strategies. The presence of large migrant populations in Libya places immense pressure on already fragile political and economic systems. “Libya’s internal security strategy increasingly sees migration as a destabilizing factor that needs to be managed, often through strict control and repatriation,” stated R1. This perspective is influenced by Libya’s fragmented political landscape, where the Government of National Unity (GNU) and various militias exert competing claims to power. These groups often view migrants as both an economic opportunity and a security risk, impacting their approach to return policies and practices. Militias, in particular, play a dual role as enforcers and profiteers in return migration governance. They capitalize on the detention and movement of migrants, effectively turning migration management into a source of revenue. “Militias operate with impunity, using detention centres as profit centres under the guise of migration control,” R4 explained. This dynamic adds a layer of complexity to domestic interests, where non-state actors prioritize financial gain over humanitarian considerations.

Externally, the EU’s interests in migration governance from Libya to Nigeria are rooted in its aim to curb irregular migration into Europe (Pastore and Roman 2020). The EU’s migration policies have evolved to externalize border management by investing in partnerships with transit countries like Libya (Carbone 2022). The EU’s strategy includes funding and logistical support for programs like the IOM’s VHR initiative, aimed at reducing migration pressure on European borders. R2 pointed out that “the EU’s financial commitment to stopping irregular migration in Libya is significant, but it comes with a humanitarian cost.” This external pressure has influenced Libya’s approach to migration, encouraging practices that align with European containment goals while often sidelining comprehensive protection measures for migrants. Effectively, the EU’s support for Libyan border management, while aimed at stemming migration flows, has unintentionally contributed to a context in which thousands of migrants remain in detention or are subjected to torture, exploitation, and slavery (Adesina 2021).

Capacities for return migration governance are influenced by both the strengths and limitations of the actors involved. The GNU’s capacity to govern is constrained by its limited territorial control and reliance on non-state actors, such as militias and local authorities, who manage significant parts of the migration system. “The central government’s limited reach

means that return migration practices vary greatly depending on which militia or local group is in control,” emphasized R3. These non-state actors often operate independently, undermining consistent policy enforcement and creating fragmented governance structures. The capacity to implement humane return practices is further challenged by widespread corruption and insufficient infrastructure. Migrants detained in centres run by militias or under state oversight often face extortion, with reports highlighting cases where individuals must pay bribes to facilitate their release or prioritize their placement on return flights. The lack of centralized control over detention facilities exacerbates these issues. One interviewee remarked that “without a unified approach, corruption festers, and humanitarian standards fall by the wayside,” highlighting the critical gap in effective governance (R4).

The role of the EU as a driving force in return migration governance is pronounced. Through financial aid and policy agreements, the EU has shaped Libya’s migration management landscape. The 2017 Italy-Libya Memorandum of Understanding is a prime example of how European policy has influenced Libyan practices. This agreement funded the Libyan Coast Guard to intercept migrants at sea and return them to shore, where they often end up in detention centres. “EU funding has effectively outsourced the control of migration, placing Libya as the front line of European border management,” R1 noted. This agreement can be seen as a continuation of the migration diplomacy framework that Libya has historically employed, where European dependence on Libyan cooperation results in policies that often prioritize containment over comprehensive migrant welfare (Tsourapas 2017). This policy has been criticized for enabling human rights abuses, as intercepted migrants are frequently subjected to detention in inhumane conditions without adequate oversight. EU financial support also extends to programs like the EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa, which allocates resources for enhancing migration governance in transit countries. However, while these funds are intended to bolster humanitarian and reintegration efforts, they have been scrutinized for focusing disproportionately on containment. “The EU’s commitment to stopping migration has led to policies that prioritize immediate deterrence over long-term solutions,” commented R2. This approach impacts the governance capacity of international organizations like the IOM, which rely on EU funding but must operate within the constraints imposed by both EU and Libyan agendas.

These driving forces have tangible consequences on how return migration governance is implemented and perceived. Domestically, the prioritization of security over humanitarian needs results in practices that often violate migrant rights (on this, see also: Paoletti and Pastore 2010). The reliance on militias for enforcement further blurs accountability and allows for exploitation. Externally, the EU’s policies, while successful in reducing migration numbers reaching Europe, have drawn criticism for exacerbating the suffering of migrants caught in transit. This has strained diplomatic relationships with both Libya and sub-Saharan African nations like Nigeria, which bear the brunt of reintegrating returnees. “The EU’s influence is clear, but it raises questions about the ethical implications of prioritizing border security over human rights,” R3 concluded.

Effects of return migration governance from Libya to Nigeria

The governance of return migration from Libya to Nigeria has complex and far-reaching effects on regional and interregional levels. These effects manifest in terms of protection, mobility, and diplomacy, shaping the experiences of migrants and influencing relationships

between key stakeholders. On a regional scale, protection for migrants within Libya remains limited and uneven, heavily influenced by who controls the detention centres and migration routes. Despite international efforts, the conditions in many centres continue to violate basic human rights (Bish et al. 2024). Reports and interview data consistently highlight the abuse, overcrowding, and lack of necessities in these facilities. R1 stated that “the conditions are harsh and often deteriorate under the control of militias, who prioritize profit over safety.” This systemic failure undermines the efforts of international organizations like the IOM and NGOs working on the ground, whose capacity to protect and assist migrants is constrained by Libya’s fragmented power structures.

The emphasis on containment policies, driven largely by EU-funded programs, has inadvertently perpetuated these protection issues. While financial support aims to strengthen Libya’s migration infrastructure, it often fails to translate into better living conditions for detained migrants. Instead, the emphasis on preventing irregular migration to Europe leads to practices that keep migrants in prolonged states of detention or push them into more dangerous, informal routes. “The focus on border security over humanitarian support creates a cycle where migrants remain in limbo, facing recurring violence and instability,” explained R2.

Mobility is another critical aspect impacted by return migration governance. Policies aimed at controlling migration flows have resulted in what some experts refer to as enforced immobility. Migrants who are intercepted at sea or caught within Libya’s borders often face indefinite detention or are forced to remain in precarious conditions without the means to move forward or return home safely. This state of enforced immobility exacerbates the vulnerabilities of migrants, trapping them in a country that struggles with its own socio-political instability. “Migrants find themselves unable to progress toward their destinations or return safely, leading to a liminal existence marked by fear and uncertainty,” R4 noted. Syed Zwick’s research reveals that these states of enforced immobility and experiences of violence shape onward migration aspirations, pushing many to seek better protection and stability elsewhere (Syed Zwick 2022).

The EU’s externalization of border control has further entrenched this cycle of immobility. By positioning Libya as the frontline barrier to European migration, EU policies encourage practices that limit the freedom of movement for migrants without adequately addressing their rights or needs. This has turned Libya into a de facto holding zone, where mobility is severely restricted. “The EU’s strategy is effective in reducing crossings to Europe, but it leaves thousands of migrants stranded in dire conditions with no clear path forward,” added R3.

Diplomatically, the approach to return migration governance affects relationships between Libya, the EU, and sub-Saharan African nations, particularly Nigeria. The emphasis on repatriation and containment has strained these relationships, as it places a significant burden on countries of origin to reintegrate returnees without sufficient support. Nigeria, for example, must navigate the reintegration of returnees who often arrive with psychological and physical scars from their time in Libya. “Reintegration is challenging; returnees need more than just transport back home—they need comprehensive support to rebuild their lives,” commented R1. The EU’s policies have faced criticism for prioritizing European border security over collaborative solutions that could benefit both transit and origin countries. This approach has strained diplomatic ties, with some African leaders expressing frustration at the disproportionate focus on containment. “There is a growing sentiment that EU policies push

the migration burden onto African countries without adequately considering the broader implications,” R4 explained.

Interregional consequences of return migration governance mirror those seen at the regional level but are amplified by the involvement of multiple actors and differing priorities. Protection mechanisms, already weak within Libya, become even more complex when viewed through the lens of multi-state governance. According to Syed Zwick, the desire for onward movement often arises from inadequate protection and recurring incidents of abuse in transit countries like Libya (Syed Zwick 2022). The EU’s externalization strategy, while successful in reducing migration numbers to Europe, has raised significant human rights concerns. This strategy effectively shifts the challenge of migrant protection and support onto transit countries like Libya, where the political will and resources to uphold such standards are limited. For R2, “policies focused solely on external control can create a situation where transit countries struggle to manage the humanitarian fallout.” The mobility of migrants under this interregional system becomes restricted not only within Libya but across broader migration routes. The heightened security and surveillance measures, combined with limited legal pathways, push migrants to seek riskier alternatives. This leads to an increase in human smuggling and trafficking, as migrants become more desperate to find routes out of Libya. “Restrictive policies create a black market for mobility, with smugglers filling the void left by legal migration pathways,” R3 observed.

Diplomatic challenges at the interregional level include the balancing act that transit and origin countries must perform in responding to EU migration policies. While some bilateral agreements include funding and support, the primary focus often remains on reducing migration to Europe. This dynamic can hinder broader collaboration and joint efforts to address the root causes of migration, such as economic disparity and conflict. As R1 suggested, “there’s a need for more balanced diplomacy that focuses on long-term solutions rather than just immediate deterrence.” The current model places considerable strain on transit and origin countries, limiting their ability to negotiate better terms for cooperation and humanitarian support.

In summary, the governance of return migration from Libya to Nigeria is characterized by a range of challenges that impact protection, mobility, and diplomatic relations. Regional efforts are undermined by Libya’s internal fragmentation and the dominant role of non-state actors, while interregional policies, heavily influenced by the EU, focus on containment at the expense of comprehensive solutions. These dynamics create a cycle of restricted mobility, inadequate protection, and strained diplomatic ties, highlighting the need for more balanced, humanitarian-focused approaches to migration governance.

Conclusion

This country dossier, part of WP4 of the GAPS “Decentring the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond” project, provides an in-depth look at the governance of return migration from Libya to Nigeria. The findings illustrate how governance is influenced by both domestic and external forces within a fragmented system. Libya, located in North Africa and sharing borders with several countries, evolved from being a welcoming destination for African workers under Muammar Gaddafi’s regime to a critical transit point post-2011. The fall of Gaddafi, who was a dominant leader known for his Pan-African and anti-

Western stances, led to power vacuums filled by militias. These groups play pivotal roles in migration management, sometimes collaborating with official authorities but often prioritizing economic interests over humanitarian concerns. The Voluntary Humanitarian Return (VHR) program, coordinated by the IOM and supported by EU funding, provides an option for migrants wishing to return home. However, many so-called “voluntary” returns are driven by untenable conditions within detention centres, where overcrowding, violence, and forced labour are common. Forced returns, which occur under coercive circumstances, illustrate the harsh realities faced by migrants, including Nigerians, who are frequently subjected to mistreatment. Actors involved in this migration governance include the Libyan Government of National Unity, militias that wield significant power over detention operations, and the Libyan Coast Guard, which intercepts migrants attempting to cross the Mediterranean Sea. The EU’s strategic influence, through financial support and policy agreements, significantly shapes Libya’s handling of migration. For example, the 2017 Italy-Libya Memorandum aimed to strengthen the Libyan Coast Guard’s capacity to intercept migrants. While these measures have reduced the number of migrants reaching Europe, they have been criticized for perpetuating poor conditions in detention centres and prioritizing containment over the protection of human rights. Domestically, Libya’s return migration governance is driven by security concerns and economic strain, leading to strict control measures. This reliance on non-state actors such as militias results in fragmented and inconsistent practices that undermine coordinated policies. Externally, the EU’s investment in programs designed to manage migration flows underscores its intent to limit irregular migration to Europe. However, this approach often sidelines humanitarian concerns and emphasizes border security over comprehensive migrant support. The consequences of these practices are extensive. Migrants in Libya frequently endure inadequate protection and prolonged periods of enforced immobility, where their movement is restricted, leaving them unable to proceed or return home safely. Detention centres often become sites of exploitation, as insufficient oversight allows abuses to persist. These challenges also impact diplomatic relationships between Libya, the EU, and origin countries like Nigeria, which face the daunting task of reintegrating returnees without sufficient resources or international support. The findings in this dossier point to the urgent need for a balanced approach that integrates effective border control with strong humanitarian frameworks. Addressing the root causes of migration, enhancing protection measures, and ensuring the humane treatment of migrants should be central to migration policies. This balanced approach would help reconcile security goals with ethical obligations, fostering a more sustainable and dignified system for managing return migration.

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